

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PROGRESS MANAGEMENT OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT SYSTEM AT NATIONAL LEVEL IN THE CONDITIONS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The article examines the issue of the need to develop the public procurement system at national level in the context of sustainable development. The prospects for using the essential elements of the sustainable public procurement policy recommended by the Organization for Economic Cooperation are eminent and highly topical for the Republic of Moldova. In this context, the principles of green public procurement are argued by the authors as real opportunities for stakeholders in the process of implementing sustainability postulates. Also, solutions for the development and implementation of a green public procurement program have been proposed, which allows the orientation of the national economy towards the global trend of changing economic mechanisms towards the circular economy and ensuring a favorable living environment.

Keywords: green public procurement, sustainability, sustainable development.

Introduction. Global economic problems such as economic crises and environmental degradation require a fundamental change in the way we produce and consume goods and services. To achieve the sustainable development goals, we must radically revise production and consumption mechanisms, by implementing concrete management procedures based on political will and a deep understanding of the new global economic trends. In this sense, green public procurement is considered as one of the most important mechanisms to promote a green economy.

In this context, public procurement aimed at protecting the environment is strategically important for any country, as it guarantees the satisfaction of government needs in terms of any goods (services, works) and is the main method of supporting enterprises and institutions, both during the world financial crises, as well as for the sustainable development of society. They should not be based only on one criterion, that of the low price, because this approach does not take into account the potential losses of the state as a result of the negative impact of the production and consumption of the purchased goods on the environment, the lack of resolution of the problems of social equality, the reduction of social balance in society, the stagnation of the economic development of the production sector and businesses.

Thus, the implementation of green public procurement and sustainable development policies represents an important opportunity to address economic, social, and environmental challenges and to create a more sustainable and equitable economy. These policies can be promoted through government programs, education and awareness-raising initiatives, as well as through the involvement and collaboration of various stakeholders, including the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and civil society.

The approach based on green public procurement is an effective tool for achieving the goals of sustainable development and creating an economy oriented towards environmental protection and social justice. This approach enables government needs to be met in products and services without harming the environment and society. In addition, it promotes the development of green technologies, support for small businesses and the creation of new jobs.

However, to succeed in this sphere, it is necessary to create an appropriate infrastructure, to train and inform the participants of the existing markets about the new requirements, as well as to regularly control compliance with the established norms and rules. In addition, for green public procurement to become truly effective, it is necessary to carry out awareness-raising and information activities for the population regarding environmental issues and sustainable development.

Theoretical aspects of research work. Currently, a sustainable public procurement policy is being implemented worldwide, recommended by the Organization for Economic Cooperation. This policy can be industrial, social, ecological or political in nature and is called "secondary policy" in the terminology adopted in the EU, or "indirect policy" - in the terminology adopted in the US. States are obliged to create the appropriate policy framework and provide support for these goals [1]. In this context, we can mention that in 2010 the Monti report (Monti Report) was published in the EU, which suggested the introduction of mandatory legislative requirements on innovations, green procurement and social issues in public procurement.

One of the main conclusions of the Monti Report is that public procurement can become a powerful tool for promoting innovation, sustainable green solutions and social responsibility. Therefore, to make effective use of public procurement, legislative measures aimed at improving innovative activity, environmental responsibility and social policy should be implemented.

In addition, the report recommends the creation of tools that allow the collection and analysis of public procurement data in order to determine their social, economic and environmental efficiency [5].

In his report "Using public procurement to achieve Europe's policy objectives", Monti concluded that public procurement policy needs to be reviewed and reformed to be better integrated with horizontal public policy, for several reasons. It also states that the reassessment of the policy is justified, in particular, by the need to simplify and modernize public procurement rules.

In the same context, Monti emphasized that the reform of public procurement policies should also aim at encouraging innovation, promoting green procurement and social responsibility. In Monti's view, these changes could bring significant benefits to both the public sector and the wider economy. It was also recommended to create tools to collect and analyze public procurement data to determine their social, economic and environmental effectiveness. Thus, the Monti Report had a significant impact on public procurement policy in Europe and led to major reforms in this area.

The important functions that public procurement fulfills in the development of the economy can be identified as follows:

1. The public procurement mechanism allows the satisfaction of the state's needs in terms of goods, services and works in established volumes and quality, ensuring stable economic relations with the involvement of the state as an economic subject.

2. Public procurement is a tool for creating an investment climate, regulating the economic structure by sector and at the regional level and serves as a factor to increase aggregate demand.

3. Through the price regulation function, public procurement indirectly influences the evolution of prices in the market economy.

4. The strategic function of public procurement consists in its ability to influence the direction of socio-economic development of a country by establishing a short-term perspective and ensuring a certain level of public services. It reflects the social orientation of state policy and is an essential factor for the existence of the socio-economic system. The public procurement mechanism provides the opportunity to define priorities and allocate resources strategically to achieve the government's policy objectives.

5. Through public procurement, the state can encourage innovation by purchasing innovative products and advanced technologies, thus implementing one of the principles of the public procurement system - the stimulation of innovation. This function can be achieved by directly financing innovative research from the budget, by organizing tender procedures or by stimulating the demand for new products and technologies, thus regulating and encouraging innovative activity.

Green (ecological) procurement imposed the process by which government organizations satisfies their needs for goods, services, works and public services in a way that ensures a balance between cost and quality throughout their life cycle, taking into account the benefits to the organization, society and the economy, with minimal impact on the environment.

Through green procurement, the government aims to encourage the use of products and services that have a lower impact on the environment, promote the development of sustainable technologies and practices, and support the green economy. These purchases may include, but are not limited to, recyclables, renewable energy, low-emission vehicles, energy-efficient construction, and waste and water management services that reduce environmental impact. Therefore, green procurement is an important tool through which the government can promote sustainable development and help reduce environmental impact.

Analyze and result of research work. Green public procurement stimulates the development of the market for ecological products and services, which is actively supported by international organizations and increases the demand for companies that invest in innovative and green technologies for the production, transport, storage, use and disposal of products.

This, in turn, leads to a reducing pressure on the environment and a decrease in the level of pollution, which has a beneficial effect on the health of people and the economy of the country as a whole. Therefore, green public procurement has not only an ecological but also a socio-economic importance. All this aims to encourage the development of the market for ecological products and services, to reduce the burden on the environment and to promote a more sustainable and healthy economy [4]. The Green Procurement Principles are intended for any stakeholder involved in the government procurement process (fig. 1.).

Figure 1. Principles of sustainable public procurement
Source: developed by authors.

Thus, each of these principles can be explained as follows:

- *Efficient public procurement is sustainable/green public procurement.* Efficient public procurement is one that combines transparency, equity, competition, and the efficient use of public resources by taking into account the three aspects of sustainable development: social, environmental, and economic. In order to be considered sustainable or green, public procurement must consider the full impact of the product or service throughout its entire life cycle, regardless of location, and manage this cycle through reuse, recycling, and responsible disposal.
- *Proactive and engaged leadership is necessary for the implementation of sustainable/green public procurement.* In order to promote public procurement, influential leaders at the highest levels are necessary. They can ensure sufficient resources for implementation and contribute to a widespread adoption of best practices.
- *Sustainable/green public procurement contributes to achieving broader policy objectives.* These objectives can include sustainable management of natural resources, resource efficiency, sustainable development, and sustainable consumption/production. Sustainable public procurement can also stimulate markets for innovative and sustainable solutions, encouraging early interaction with the market and creating "green" and valuable job opportunities.
- *Sustainable public procurement involves all stakeholders.* The implementation of sustainable public procurement requires the support of all stakeholders. Politicians, suppliers, manufacturers, contractors, providers, and civil society organizations work together to achieve this. The necessary skills for sustainable public procurement include communication and analysis, the ability to influence, negotiate and act professionally, an understanding of the market and all sustainability factors

- *The success of implementing sustainable public procurement is based on well-established organizational principles of management.* Sustainable public procurement is based on a risk assessment approach, updating and focusing on the highest impact or priorities. Immediate success can be demonstrated through the use of "quick wins" methods. However, this should not replace a global long-term approach. Sustainable public procurement, as part of the organization's management system, helps integrate it into everyday practice.

- *Sustainable public procurement ensures monitoring of efficiency and results.* Continuous improvement is only possible when the results achieved through SPP are known. The use of monitoring and evaluation systems is crucial to track progress and identify "weak points". Results can include environmental indicators such as reduced emissions, reduced material use, and reduced waste generation; economic results such as cost savings (including intangible benefits and costs), job creation, wealth creation, and transfer of skills/technologies; social results such as expanded minority rights, poverty reduction, and "good governance".

In the European Union, a steady process of improving organizational and legal support for green public procurement is underway. There are specialized scientific institutions, electronic platforms that provide information to interested parties and political support in this direction. The activity of the European Commission is an example worthy of following at the global level in ensuring the achievement of the sustainable development objectives. A number of European countries have developed their own guidelines for green public procurement, which help both purchasers and product suppliers/manufacturers guide their work in this area. It is important to note that the governmental level has a crucial role, because the green public procurement criteria remain voluntary, but lead to the formation of social and ethical rules of interaction between authorities

and businesses, which become a sustainable practice and define the relations between the parties.

In addition, by promoting green public procurement, the European Union aims to reduce the negative impact on the environment and promote sustainable development. Green public procurement involves the purchase of goods and services that have a lower impact on the environment, as well as the purchase of products from sustainable and ecological sources. This can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and protect natural resources such as water and energy.

Green public procurement can also promote sustainable economic development by encouraging innovation and the development of new green technologies. In this respect, suppliers of green goods and services can be supported and encouraged to innovate and improve their products and services so that they become more sustainable and resource efficient. Green public procurement represents an important opportunity to promote sustainable development in the European Union and the world in general. By promoting these purchases, the negative impact of human activities on the environment can be reduced and development can be encouraged.

For the Republic of Moldova, which is currently, from many points of view, in a favorable position of acceptance at the European and global level, it becomes opportune and inevitable to urgently review the management of public procurement in the event of accession to the EU. In this context, it is important to raise awareness of the creation and implementation of a massive programme to green public procurement, in which the state must provide support, including organizational and financial support. Ecological public procurement can be a strong incentive to introduce innovative and waste-free technologies in production. Green procurement reduces the environmental impact of meeting the needs of government organizations for goods and services by managing the product life cycle. The ecological criteria of the products must have a public basis and receive bonus points. These criteria may be specific according to territory, economic specificity and national trade, but will require harmonization to achieve the goals of sustainable development. An algorithm for applying green criteria in public procurement can determine the need for structural changes in the production process and accelerate the actual filling of the relevant market. Thus, we can adapt to the global trend of changing economic mechanisms towards the circular economy and ensuring a favorable living environment.

Through the greening of public procurement, the aim is to implement innovative and waste-free technologies in production, with a reduced impact on the environment. By managing the life cycle of products, the traditional consumption of goods and services with the same functionality can be reduced, which can have a positive effect on the environment and, implicitly, on public health. In this sense, the ecological criteria of products, which are based on the awarding of bonus points, can become an effective method of incentivizing manufacturers to obtain government contracts and improve their production process. This can lead to in-

creased competitiveness and innovation in the industrial sector, which can have long-term economic benefits for the country.

In addition, a clear picture of the main directions of systematization and formation of the organic products market must be obtained, by using statistical aggregators and other available data, by making a current picture of the presence of both domestic as well as foreign "green" products on the national branch markets. It is important to have information at the national level about eco-labelling, as well as about the level, nature and efficiency of the certification organizations in Moldova.

The next step should be the methodological evaluation of the activity of certification organizations through the involvement of public organizations. This evaluation should focus on specific certification objectives by randomly selecting certification objects, aiming to highlight the best and worst practices of the relevant structures, followed by the creation of an open public ranking of certification organizations, including an evaluation system through specialized IT portals with the use of a confirmation protocol. This work seems necessary in the context of the massive expansion of unethical practices taking place on the certification market, as well as to assess the contribution of certification organizations to the creation, emergence and establishment of organic products on the national market. Understanding this area is essential to separate the wheat from the chaff, to ensure sound oversight of the overall organic certification policy, and to take further steps in promoting a real eco-label.

In this context, the Moldovan government has the capacity to form a national plan to guide the state's green procurement in collaboration with key trading partners. This plan should include addressing sector priorities in the development of product criteria and requirements, as well as a temporal and semantic structure to increase the capacity to implement sustainable procurement strategies. Its main tasks must be the formation of ecological criteria by sectors, their methodological support and implementation, as well as the planned training of personnel. It is important to establish indicators to measure progress, taking into account the approximate deadlines for the implementation of the block of strategic actions planned in the sectoral and territorial context.

In order to ensure a productive development of the national green procurement program, close collaboration between working groups and experts with international organizations such as the OECD, the European Commission and the One Planet program is necessary [7]. It is also important to get involved as a country in the work of international associations dealing with sustainable public procurement and to benefit from the exchange of information and practices with experts in this field. By examining global practices and aligning standards and criteria with international norms, it is possible to accelerate the development of one's own methodological foundation and avoid the mistakes made by other international partners.

Conclusions. Starting from the mentioned, we can deduce that when the concept of sustainable development is applied in public procurement, they are defined as a process by which the buyer fulfills his needs for goods, works and services so that the ratio between price and quality of the purchased products reflects positively not only on the organization making the purchase, but also on the national economy and society in general, thus contributing to reducing the negative impact of production activities on the environment.

In addition, it is important to establish clear mechanisms for assessing the environmental impact of products and services purchased through public procurement, so as to ensure that they meet the highest environmental and public health standards. These assessments should include not only the direct impact of products and services on the environment, but also the impact on the entire supply chain and product life cycle.

Thus, through sustainable public procurement, the government can achieve environmental goals such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving the efficiency of energy and water resource use, and supporting the recycling sector. In the social sphere, sustainable public procurement can contribute to reducing poverty, strengthening social justice and increasing respect for workers' rights. From an economic point of view, sustainable public procurement can reduce costs and prices, promote the spread of skills and technologies, and support the economic development of disadvantaged groups through the allocation of specific public contracts.

Therefore, simplifying sustainable procurement by government can help achieve environmental goals such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving energy and water resource efficiency, and supporting the recycling industry. In the social sphere, sustainable

government procurement can influence poverty reduction, strengthen social justice and increase respect for workers' rights. Economically, sustainable government procurement can reduce costs and prices, promote skills and technologies, and support the economic development of disadvantaged population groups in the country by awarding government contracts to these groups.

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